

WAYS OF STUDYING THE TEXT OF CHINGIZ AITMATOV'S STORY "JAMILA"

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Abstract: The name of the great Kyrgyz writer Chingiz Aitmatov stands alongside the great representatives of world literature who gained international recognition in the twentieth century. The artistic embodiment of major spiritual problems troubling humanity, reflected through the centuries-old past and present life of the Kyrgyz people and neighboring nations, their dreams and aspirations, joys and anxieties, and diverse human destinies, is the unifying feature of the writer's works. This article discusses the ways of studying the writer's story *Jamila* in literary education.

Keywords: Kyrgyz literature, writer, novella, character, logic of life, literary text, author's position.

Introduction

At the lower stages of human civilization, activities aimed at educating and teaching individuals were organized on the basis of simple and straightforward requirements. However, today the organization of the educational process is subject to far more complex demands. In particular, the social need to train qualified specialists who can work with complex technology, fully understand the essence of production processes, and positively solve problems arising in emergency situations requires the organization of education on the basis of technological approaches. Proceeding from this, the use of project-based and developmental educational technologies in literary education increases the effectiveness of lessons and provides an opportunity to delve more deeply into literary texts. The use of educational technologies is also considered an important tool in studying the works of Chingiz Aitmatov.

The work that first brought Chingiz Aitmatov international fame was the novella *Jamila*. Written in 1958, it was published in book form in Russian and French in 1959, and within two years it was translated into nearly thirty languages of the former Soviet Union and abroad. Louis Aragon, who translated the novella into French, described it as "the most beautiful love story in the world" and even gave his article the same title.

Discussion

The novella depicts human freedom and rights, as well as an active attitude toward ancient traditions, through the pure and sincere love between Jamila and Daniyar. Love is the highest feeling and a powerful force. However, in order to achieve one's goal or defend it, one sometimes needs a strength of will and determination no less powerful than love itself. What path should people choose when their love is not understood—or deliberately misunderstood—by those around them, as in the environment surrounding Daniyar and Jamila, and when it contradicts the moral and spiritual norms in which the characters were raised? The love of Jamila and Daniyar faces precisely such a trial. Without unnecessary conflict or scandal, without disrespecting traditions, and most importantly without allowing their love to

be trampled upon, they leave with their heads held high for the world of their free feelings. The artistic portrayal of historical changes in the fate of a people and an era through sharp turns in the destinies of the main characters is one of the leading features of Chingiz Aitmatov's creative path.

When helping students read and understand the text of the novella, it is necessary to pay special attention to these issues.

The following key concepts are used during the lesson: Kyrgyz literature, novella genre, aesthetic essence of literature, realistic literature, hero, free feelings, leading idea, humanism, artistic value of the work, and pure love.

In analyzing the characters of the novella, methods such as clustering and brainstorming can be effectively used. For example, the cluster method makes it possible to characterize each image more deeply. Students' attention should also be drawn to the colors used in the cluster: presenting the male characters in the same color indicates that they belong to one social circle, while the use of green for Jamila, the mother, and the villagers carries a special meaning. Students should focus on the symbolic meanings expressed by these colors.

In addition, the study of literary texts also envisages the analysis of works:

1. as a whole;
2. through characters;
3. comparatively;
4. on the basis of problem-based learning requirements.

In literary text analysis, it is also important to take into account the characteristics specific to literary genres. Especially in the analysis of epic works, attention should be paid to details and the role played by characters in them. In the analysis of the novella *Jamila*, if students' attention is directed toward important details in the text—for example, people's attitude toward labor during wartime, people's views on life and love, and the factors that changed these views—they will more quickly understand and grasp the author's intended idea and draw conclusions.

“Jamila was a graceful and elegant woman. Her two black braids were wrapped around her head, and the white scarf tied over them suited her wheat-colored round face so perfectly that one could hardly look away. When Jamila laughed, youthful vitality sparkled in her almond-shaped eyes, and at such moments she would unconsciously straighten her posture and begin singing the playful folk songs of the village” [2,4].

By giving students assignments such as: “Read the following passage carefully and create a short text based on the question ‘How did you imagine Jamila?’” students begin to study the text more thoroughly.

It is also possible to use the “Brainstorming” method by dividing students into three groups and asking them the following quick questions in order to determine how well they have mastered the text:

1. Which work made the writer famous worldwide?
2. What aspects of the novella *Jamila* did you like? 1.2.3.
3. Which character in the novella did you like the most? Why?
4. Which historical period is depicted in the novella?
5. Are there descriptions of nature in the novella? What purpose do they serve?
6. In which parts of the work does the spiritual world of the characters appear most vividly?
7. Why did Seit become fond of Daniyar?
8. What is the theme of the song sung by Daniyar?
9. Describe Jamila through Seit's perspective.

During the lesson, asking students to compose short texts on the following topics not only helps improve their written speech but also opens the way for the development of their creative abilities:

1. Create a text revealing the image and character of Jamila.
2. Give a description of Daniyar's character.
3. Describe the character of the boy.
4. Do you think the paths chosen by the novella's characters were right?

It is evident that developmental educational technologies in the process of literary analysis are aimed at developing students' critical thinking, creativity, and aesthetic taste. Interactive methods such as clustering, KWL (Know–Want to know–Learned), brainstorming, project-based learning, and multimedia tools ensure a deeper understanding of the text, help students feel the world of the characters, and encourage them to express personal opinions. Unlike traditional teaching methods, this approach transforms the learner into an active participant.

The use of project-based technology enables students to conduct independent research by preparing creative works related to the novella's theme, such as presentations, stage performances, and essays.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in order to ensure a deeper understanding of the text of the world-famous novella by the great writer, it is possible to organize practical lessons in an engaging and effective way using other interactive methods and educational technologies. Broad use of modern information technologies—such as video materials about the writer, audio recordings featuring the writer's own voice, television programs, and virtual tours to the writer's museum through electronic libraries—can contribute significantly to a deeper understanding of the novella and foster respect for Chingiz Aitmatov's творчество.

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